
REVALIDATION OF TWO SUBSPECIES NAMES OF *OBEREA* (*AMAUROSTOMA*) *ERYTHROCEPHALA* (SCHRANK, 1776) (COLEOPTERA: CERAMBYCIDAE)

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ABSTRACT: *Oberea* (*Amaurostoma*) *erythrocephala cincta* (Gebler, 1830), rest. nom. and *Oberea* (*Amaurostoma*) *erythrocephala theophilei* Pic, 1914, rest. nom. (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) are proposed as valid names.

KEY WORDS: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, taxonomy, restored name

Oberea (*Amaurostoma*) *erythrocephala erythrocephala* (Schrank, 1776) (Figs. 1-10) is distributed all over Europe (without Iberian Peninsula - ssp. *bicolor* Reiche, 1878, without north-eastern Italy - ssp. *calvescens* G. Müller, 1948 and without steppe regions of Ukraine and Russia - ssp. *cincta* (Gebler, 1830), **rest. nom.** It is known in European Russia from several regions: Voronezh, Samara and Ulyanovsk. Many known specimens from Georgia (Figs. 8-10) (Tbilisi, Borzhomi, Akhaldaba, Akhaldaba, Tsagveri, Bakuriani) are identical to the European nominative subspecies.

Oberea (*Amaurostoma*) *erythrocephala cincta* (Gebler, 1830), **rest. nom.** was described as *Saperda cincta* Gebler, 1830 from Loktevsk environs in Altay area of south-west Russian Siberia. Now it is Gornyyak environs in Altay Region of Russia. *Oberea cincta* (Gebler, 1830) was accepted by Aurivillius (1923) for the area from Volga to Siberia. Plavilstshikov (1927) downgraded the name to aberration rank, though south steppe populations of the species are rather peculiar.

Oberea (*Amaurostoma*) *erythrocephala theophilei* Pic, 1914, **rest. nom.** was described as *Oberea erythrocephala* var. *theophilei* Pic, 1914 from "Arménie". *Oberea erythrocephala theophilei* Pic, 1914 was published by Breuning, 1960 (Villiers, 1978; Löbl & Smetana, 2010; Danilevsky, 2020, 2023).

One interesting specimen was discovered in N. N. Plavilstshikov's collection - *Oberea erythrocephala* var. *richteri* Bau, 1888 (Fig. 1), syntype, male with 5 labels: 1) [upper side] "German / Berlin", [down side] "Bau"; 2) "*Oberea* v. / *Richteri*"; 3) "Mus. Caucas. / 41 - 16 / e coll. Koenig"; 4) "*Oberea* / *erythrocephala* / Schr. / N. Plavilstshikov det."; 5) "SYNTYPE / *Oberea erythrocephala* var. / *RICHTERI* / Bau, 1888 / M. Lazarev des. 2025" - ZMM.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Acronyms of collections:

MD - collection of M. L. Danilevsky (Moscow, Russia).

ML - collection of M. A. Lazarev (Moscow, Russia).

SM - collection of S. V. Murzin (Moscow, Russia).

VU - collection of V. E. Ustinov (Moscow, Russia).

ZMM - collection of Zoological Museum of Moscow State University (Moscow, Russia).

Figures 1-4. *O. (A.) e. erythrocephala* (Schrank, 1776): 1. *Oberea erythrocephala* var. *richteri* Bau, 1888, syntype, male; 2. female, Slovakia (Photo by Milan Sláma); 3. male, Russia, Voronezh region, Bychok, 21.6.1979, S. Nikireev; 4. male, Russia, Samara, 7.7.2004, D. Magdeev.

Figures 5-10. *O. (A.) e. erythrocephala* (Schrank, 1776): 5-6. male, Crimea, Tarkhankut, 2.6.1985, I. Plushch; 7. female with same label; 8. male, Georgia, Borzhomi, 14.6.1937; 9. male, Georgia, Tbilisi, 6.1984, V. Kuznetsov; 10. female, Georgia, Bakuriani environs, 2.6.1928, D. Romashov.

RESULTS

Oberea (Amaurostoma) erythrocephala cincta (Gebler, 1830), rest. nom.

(Figs. 11-13)

Saperda cincta Gebler, 1830: 186 - "Loktevsk".

Saperda luteicollis Gebler, 1833: 303 - "Loktevsk".

Oberea ?var. *luteicollis*, Ganglbauer, 1884: 584 - "Südwest-Sibirien (Loktevsk)".

Oberea ?var. *cincta*, Ganglbauer, 1884: 584 - "Südwest-Sibirien (Loktevsk).
Wolga".

Oberea erythrocephala v. *cincta*, Pic, 1917b: 120 - "Rus, M^{le}".

Oberea (Amaurostoma) cincta, Aurivillius, 1923: 529, part. - "Wolga, Sibirien".

Oberea erythrocephala, Plavilstshikov, 1927: 63 (= *cincta* Gebl.); 1965: 417, part.
- Forest-steppe, steppes, Crimea, Caucasus; Esterberg, 1935: 197 - Gorky and
Kirov regions; Kostin, 1973: 205 - possible in northwest Kazakhstan; Kasatkin
& Arzanov, 1997: 66 - Rostov and Volgograd regions, Stavropol Krai; Matveev,
1998: 87 - Mari-El, Tatarstan, Nizhny Novgorod regions; Kaliuzhnaja & al.,
2000: 190 - Volgograd and Astrakhan regions; Isaev & al., 2004: 41 -
Tatarstan, Ulyanovsk and Samara regions; Negrobov & al., 2005: 605 - Liski
district, Voronezh region; Prisnyj, 2005: 41 - Belgorod region; Zamoroka,
2022: 66, part. - Ukraine; Volovnik, 2024: 44 - "Southern Ukraine: Zaporizhia
Oblast".

Oberea (Amaurostoma) erythrocephala v. *cincta*, Winkler, 1929: 1218, part. - "R.
m. Sib."

Oberea (Amaurostoma) erythrocephala erythrocephala, Althoff & Danilevsky,
1997: 38, part; Bartenev, 2004: 40 - Ukraine; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 296,
part.; Bartenev & Terekhova, 2011: 139 - Left-bank Ukraine and Crimea;
Shapovalov, 2012: 172 - Orenburg region.

Oberea (Amaurostoma) erythrocephala, Villiers, 1978: 550, part. (= *cincta*
Gebler, 1830; = *luteicollis*, Gebler, 1830) - "Tout le bassin mediterraneen,
l'Europe centrale, le Caucase, la Siberie occidentale"; Lobanov & al., 1982: 271,
part.; Sama, 2003: 119, part - Europe, North Africa, Asia Minor, Caucasus,
Transcaucasia, northern Iran, Middle East, southern Urals, northern
Kazakhstan; Danilevsky, 2023: 466, part; 2024: 137, part.

Type locality. Russia, Altay Region, Gornyyak environs ("Loktevsk").

Head and thorax red; elytra orange, or sometimes black with longer and denser pale pubescence; sometimes head black, but thorax red; lateral elytral areas also with short pale pubescence; long and dense erect setae are distributed along first elytral third; abdomen usually totally orange-yellow, sometimes with black anterior segments, or with black spots on anterior segments; body length of available specimens: 9.3-12.9 mm.

Material. Russia: 1 female, Saratov Region, Bolshaya Kamenka, 51°48.581'N, 45°42.24'E, 20-22.6.2013, V. Ustinov - VU; 1 male, Uryupinsk, 20.6.1912 - ZMM; 1 male, Stalingrad, 6.1928 - MD; 1 male, Stalingrad, VI.1950, I.V. Stebaev - VU; 2 females, Sarepta, 25.8.1929 - MD; 1 male, Volgograd Region, Olkhovka, 200 m,

1.6.1999, M. Danilevsky - ML; 2 females, Volgograd Region, Gornaya Polyana, 18.7.1988, M. Danilevsky - ML; 1 male, Stavropol, 1.7.1912, V. Lichik - ZMM; 1 male, Adygea, Shapsug Reservoir, Khomuty, 21.6.1988, Gusarov - ML; 1 male, Cauc. bor., Kislovodsk - ZMM; 1 female, Kislovodsk, 7.7.1981, Derzhavets - ML; 11 males, Stavropol Region, Mineralnye Vody, Kislovodsk, 16.6.1984, S. Kvylya - VU; 1 male, North Ossetia-Alania, Lars, 21.5.1909 - ZMM; 1 male, Crimea, Sevastopol, 10.6.1902, V.T. Pliginsky - SM; 9 males, 8 females, Crimea, Tarkhankut Peninsula, 2.6.1985, I. Plyusch - MD; 1 male, 1 female, Crimea, Tarkhankut, 90 m, 10.6.2017, K. Efetov - ML; 1 male, 1 female, Crimea, Donuzlav, 13.6.1981, K. Efetov - MD; 1 male, 1 female, Crimea, Planerskoye, Uzun-Syrt, 18.5.2016, 12.5.2018, K. Efetov - ML; 1 male, Crimea, Belaya Skala, 18.5.1983, M. Nesterov - MD; 1 male, Donbas, Don-Sad, 29.6.1940 - MD; 1 male, Donbas, Gornaya, 30.5.1951, K. Arnoldi - ML; 2 female, Voroshilovgrad, Derkul, 26-30.5.1951, K. Arnoldi - ML; **Ukraine:** 1 male, 1 female, Kiev - ZMM; 2 males, Kiev, Khotov, 30.6.1977, M. Nesterov - MD; 2 males, Odessa, 13.6.1965, V. Yanushev - MD; 1 female, Zaporozhe, 7.7.1986, A. Shadenkov - MD; 1 female, Zaporozhe, V.1954 - SM; **Kazakhstan:** 1 male (2.6.1916), 1 female, Turgai reg., Ber-Chogur, 25.5.-2.6.1916, P. Zhikharev - ZMM; 1 female, Dzhanybek, 2.7.1970, T. Ponomarev - SM; 2 males, Naurzum, 11.6.1935, A. Formozov - SM; 2 males, 1 female, Yanvartsevo, 30.5.1996, M. Danilevsky - ML; 1 male, 5 females, Yanvartsevo, 50 m, 30.5.1996, M. Danilevsky - VU; 3 males, 7 females, Yanvartsevo, 50 m, 30.5.1996, M. Danilevsky - ML; 4 males, 3 females, Uralsk, 17.V., 25.V., 1.VI., 10.VII., V. Zhuravlev - ZMM; 2 female, Uralsk, 2.6.1996, M. Danilevsky - ML; 4 males, 6 females, Uralsk, Furmanovo, 9.6.1996, M. Danilevsky - ML; 25 males, 15 females, Uralsk, Chapaev, 10-12.6.1999, M. Danilevsky - ML; 1 female, Khromtau, 18.6.1999, M. Danilevsky - MD; 1 female, Arkalyk, 300 m, 22.6.1999, M. Danilevsky - MD. **Azerbaijan:** 1 male, Elizavetpol (new name Ganja) 15.02.1902 - ZMM; 1 male, 2 females, Adzhikend - ZMM; 1 female, Elizavetpol, Maljushenko - ZMM; 2 females, Elizavetpol, 26, 31.5.1914, A. Wassilinin - ZMM; 1 female, Aresh (new name Agdash), 27.5.1902, 3.6.1902, E. Koenig - ZMM; 1 female, Aresh, A. Shelkovnikov - ZMM.

Distribution. Steppe zone of Ukraine, Russia and central Azerbaijan (Ganja, Adzhikend, Agdash).

***Oberea erythrocephala theophilei* Pic, 1914, rest. nom.**

(Figs. 14-16)

Oberea erythrocephala v. *theophilei* Pic, 1914: 11 - "Arménie"; 1917b: 119 - "Arménie, Russ."; Breuning, 1962: 209.

Oberea erythrocephala v. *erivanica* Pic, 1917a: 11 - "Arménie: Erivan"; Breuning, 1962: 209.

Oberea (Amaurostoma) erythrocephala ab. *erivanica*, Aurivillius, 1923: 529 - "Armenien"; Winkler, 1929: 1217 - "Arm."

Oberea (Amaurostoma) erythrocephala ab. *theophilei*, Aurivillius, 1923: 530 - "Armenien"; Winkler, 1929: 1217 - "Arm."

Oberea erythrocephala v. *sinuatesignata* Pic, 1945: 7 - "Caucase".

Oberea (Amaurostoma) erythrocephala, Plavilstshikov, 1948: 177, 178, part. - All of Armenia, southern and central Europe, the Caucasus, western Asia,

southwestern Siberia; Lobanov & al., 1982: 271, part.; Danilevsky & Miroschnikov, 1985: 365, part. - Southern half of the European part of the USSR, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkmenistan, Siberia, Western Europe, North Africa, Middle East, Turkey, Iran; Danilevsky, 2023: 466, part.; 2024: 137, part.

Oberea (Amaurostoma) erythrocephala var. *theophilei*, Villiers, 1978: 552, part. - "Tout le bassin mediterraneen, l'Europe centrale, le Caucase, la Siberie occidentale".

Oberea erythrocephala theophilei, Breuning, 1960: 27.

Oberea erythrocephala erivanica, Breuning, 1960: 28.

Oberea erythrocephala, Breuning, 1967: 823, part. - "Europe centr. et mer., Afr. sept., Anatolie, Syrie, Caucase, Sibérie"; Villiers, 1967: 371, part. - "Europe centrale et meridionale, Sibérie occidentale, Turkestan, Afrique du Nord, Arménie, Iran: Tabriz".

Oberea (Amaurostoma) erythrocephala, Sama, 2003: 119, part - Europe, North Africa, Asia Minor, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, northern Iran, Middle East, southern Urals, northern Kazakhstan.

Oberea (Amaurostoma) erythrocephala erythrocephala, Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 296, part.; Sama & al., 2010: 196, part. - "Europe, région méditerranéenne, Caucase, Transcaucasie, Iran, Liban: Akkar: Fnaideq"; Danilevsky, 2020: 427, part. - "E: AN AU BH BU BY CR CT CZ FR GE GR HU IT LS LT MC MD ME PL PT RO SB SK SL SP SZ TR UK A: AB AR GG IN ?KI KZ LE SY TR WS".

Type locality. "Arménie" - according to original description.

Head and thorax usually red, or partly red, rare - totally black; sometimes thorax black with red head; elytra always totally black with recumbent pubescence nearly indistinct; erect elytral setae are distributed at anterior elytral forth; abdomen partly orange-yellow with black anterior segments, or with black stripe narrowed posteriorly, rarely totally red; body length of available specimens: 9.1-13.9 mm.

Material. Armenia: 2 males, Erevan, 14.6.1909, J. Parfentiev - ZMM; 2 males, 2 females, Dilizhan, 21.6.1939 - MD; 2 males, Khosrov, 14.8.1967, M. Danilevsky - MD; 1 male, Khosrov, 19.6.1986, A. Danchenko - ML; 2 females, Khosrov, 24.5.1990, 24.6. 1992, M. Kalashian - MD; 1 male, Khosrov, 11.7.1997, M. Kalashian - MD; 1 male, Dzhzvezh, 6.6.1960, G. Dlussky - MD; 1 male, Vayk (= Azizbekov), 22.6.1986, O. Gorbunov - ML; 1 female, Megri, 20.6.1986, O. Gorbunov - ML; 1 male, 2 km N Byurakan, Antarut, 14.7.1986, M. Kalashian - ML; 3 female, Geghard, 8.6.1989, M. Kalashian - ML; **Azerbaijan:** 2 males, 1 female, Talysh, Gosmalyan, 31.5.-2.6.1979, M. Danilevsky - MD; 1 male, 2 females, Talysh, Gosmalyan, 23.6.1984, A. Danchenko - MD; 1 male, 1 female, Talysh, Gosmalyan, 23.5.1987, A. Danchenko - ML; 1 female, Talysh, Gosmalyan, 8.6.1988, A. Danchenko - ML; 3 males, Talysh, Gosmalyan, 28.5.-7.6.1986, V. Belov - MD; 2 males, 1 female, Nakhichevan, Buzgov, 16.7.1986, M. Danilevsky - ML; 2 males, 3 females, Nakhichevan, Buzgov, 20.6.1986, 1500-1600 m, O. Gorbunov - ML; 1 male, Ordubad, 16.6.1940 - MD.

Distribution. Armenia, southern Azerbaijan (Nakhichevan, Talysh), North Turkey, North Iran.

Figures 11-13. *O. (A.) e. cincta* (Gebler, 1830), **rest. nom.**: 11. Male, male, Azerbaijan, Adzhikent; 12. female, Aresh (new name Agdash), 27.5.1902, 3.6.1902, E. Koenig; 13. female, Kazakstan, Khromtau, 18.6.1999, M. Danilevsky; Figures 14-16. *O. (A.) e. theophilei* Pic, 1914, **rest. nom.**: 14. male, Armenia, Khosrov, 19.6.1986, A. Danchenko; 15. male, Azerbaijan, Talysh, Gosmalyan, 28.5.-7.6.1986, V. Belov; 16. female, Azerbaijan, Talysh, Gosmalyan, 23.6.1984, A. Danchenko.

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LITERATURE CITED

- Althoff, J. & Danilevsky, M.L.** 1997. A check-list of Longicorn beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycoidea) of Europe. Slovensko Entomološko Društvo Stefana Michielija. Ljubljana: 64 pp.
- Aurivillius, C.** 1923. Cerambycidae: Lamiinae II. Pars 74. In: Schenkling S. (ed.): Coleopterorum Catalogus. Volumen XXIII. Cerambycidae II. Berlin: W. Junk, pp. 323-704.
- Bau, A.** 1888. Handbuch für Käfer-Sammler. Beschreibung der in Deutschland, Österreich-Ungarn und der Schweiz vorkommenden Coleopteren. Die Käfer. Handbuch für Insekten Sammler. 2. Magdeburg, Creutz (R. & M. Kretschmann): i-iv + 1-494, 144 figs.
- Bartenev, A. F.** 2004 A review of the long-horned beetles species (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) of the fauna of Ukraine. The Kharkov Entomological Society Gazette, 11 (1-2) [2003]: 24-43. [in Russian]
- Bartenev, A. F. & Terekhova, V. V.** 2011. An addition and remarks to the fauna of cerambycid beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) of Left-bank Ukraine and Crimea. The Journal of V.N. Karazin Kharkiv National University. Series: biology, 13 (947): 133-146. [in Russian]
- Breuning, S.** 1960. Revision systématique des espèces du genre *Obera* Mulsant du globe (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). (1ère partie). Frustula Entomologica, 3 (4): 1-59.
- Breuning, S.** 1962. Revision systématique des espèces du genre *Obera* Mulsant du globe (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). (3ème partie). Frustula Entomologica, 5 (4): 141-232 + vi.
- Breuning, S.** 1967. Catalogue des Lamiaires du Monde (Col. Céramb.). Verlag des Museums G. Frey, Tutzing bei München (10): 771-832 + Index Tribus, Genera, Subgenera: 833-864.
- Danilevsky, M. L. & Miroschnikov, A. I.** 1985. Timber-Beetles of Caucasus (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). Key. Krasnodar: 419 pp. [in Russian]
- Danilevsky, M. L.** 2020 (ed.). Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera, vol. 6 (1), Chrysomeloidea I (Vesperiidae, Disteniidae, Cerambycidae). Revised and updated edition. Leiden / Boston: Brill, i-xxii, 1-712.
- Danilevsky, M. L.** 2023. Longicorn beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycoidea) of Russia and adjacent countries. Part 3. Moscow: IAE. 873 pp. [in Russian]
- Danilevsky, M. L.** 2024. Key to longhorned beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) of Russia. Volume 1. European part and North Caucasus. Moscow: IAE. 246 pp. [in Russian]
- Esterberg, L. K.** 1935. Insects of Gorky and Kirov regions. Nature of Gorky and Kirov regions. Gorky publishing house: 195-210. [in Russian]
- Ganglbauer, L.** 1884. Bestimmungs-Tabellen der europäischen Coleopteren. VIII. Cerambycidae. (Schluss.) Mit Berücksichtigung der Formen Algiers und des paläarktischen Asiens, exclusive jener von Japan. - Verhandlungen der kaiserlich-königlichen zoologisch-botanischen Gesellschaft in Wien, 33 [1883]: 437-586.
- Gebler, F. A. von.** 1830. Bemerkungen über die Insecten Sibiriens, vorzüglich des Altai. (Part III). Pp. 1-228. In: C.F. Ledebour (ed.): Reise durch das Altai-Gebirge und die soongorische Kirgisen-Steppe. Auf Kosten der Kaiserlichen Universität Dorpat unternommen im Jahre 1826 in Begleitung der Herren D. Carl Anton Meyer und D. Alexander von Bunge R.K. Collegien-Assessors. Zweiter Theil. Berlin: G. Reimer, iv + 522 + [2] pp.
- Gebler, F. A.** 1833. XXX. Notæ et additamenta ad catalogum Coleopterorum Sibiriae occidentalis et confinis Tatariae operis (Voyage de C. F. Ledebours dans les monts Altaïques et les Steppes des Kirguises.) 2e partie. Bulletin de la Société Impériale des Naturalistes de Moscou, 6: 235-309.
- Isaev, A. Yu., Egorov, L. V. & Egorov, K. A.** 2004. Beetles (Insecta, Coleoptera) of forest-steppe of Middle Volga. Catalogue. Ulianovsk. 72 pp. [in Russian]
- Kaluzhnaja, N. S., Komarov, E. V., Cherezova, L. B.** 2000. Coleoptera of lower Volga river. Volgograd. 204 pp. [in Russian]
- Kasatkin, D. G. & Arzanov, Yu. G.** 1997. "Der Bockkaffer (Cerambycidae). Material fur Fauna der Kaffer (Coleoptera) Norden Kaukasus und untere Don." [wrong translation of the Russian title of the article; must be: "Die Bockkaffer (Cerambycidae) (Teil 2). Die Materialien zur Käferfauna (Coleoptera) des Nordkaukasus und des unteren Don] Records of Kharkov Entomological Society, 5 (2): 63-70. [in Russian]
- Kostin, I. A.** 1973. The Dendrophagus Beetles of Kazakhstan (Buprestidae, Cerambycidae, Ipidae). AlmaAta: 288 pp. [in Russian]
- Lobanov, A. L., Danilevsky, M. L. & Murzin, S. V.** 1982. Systematic list of longicorn beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) of the USSR. 2. Revue d'Entomologie, 61 (2): 252-277.
- Löbl, I. & Smetana, A.** (ed.) 2010. Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera, Vol. 6. Chrysomeloidea. Stenstrup: Apollo Books. 924 pp.
- Matveev, V. A.** 1998. Xilophagous insects of Volga-Viatka region. Joshkar-Ola. 93 pp. [in Russian]
- Negrobov, S. O., Tzurikov, M. N., Logvinovsky, V. D., Fomichev, A. I., Prokin, A. A. & Gilmudinov, K. S.** 2005. Order Coleoptera. Cadastre of Invertebrata of Voronezh region. Voronezh: 534-673. [in Russian]
- Pic, M.** 1914. Notes diverses et diagnoses. Matériaux pour servir à l'étude des Longicornes, 9 (1): 3-11.
- Pic, M.** 1917a. Notes diverses, descriptions et diagnoses (Suite.). L'Échange, Revue Linnéenne, 33 (381): 9-11.
- Pic, M.** 1917b. Catalogue bibliographique et synonymique d'Europe et des régions avoisinantes. Lyon: Imprimerie Jacquet. 10ème cahier. 2ème partie. pp. 119-120.
- Pic, M.** 1945. Nouvelles variétés de Coléoptères Longicornes. L'Échange, Revue Linnéenne, 61 (500): 5-7.

-
- Plavilstshikov, N. N.** 1927. Coleoptera II. Addenda et corrigenda concernant le Coleopterorum Calogus, parties 73 et 74 (Lamiinae) de Chr. Aurivillius. Encyclopédie Entomologique (série B), 1 (2): 49-68.
- Plavilstshikov, N. N.** 1948. A Key for Longicorn Beetles of Armenia. Erevan. 232 pp. [in Russian]
- Plavilstshikov, N. N.** 1965. 75-th Fam. Cerambycidae - Timber Beetles, Longicorns. In: A Key to Insects of the European Part of the USSR, v. 2, Coleoptera and Strepsiptera. Moscow-Leningrad: Nauka: 389-419. [in Russian]
- Prisnyj, A. V.** 2005. Insects - Ectognatha. Beetles - Coleoptera. In: Prisnyj A. V., O. V. Vorobieva, 2005 (eds.) Scientific collection funds of "Museum of Zoology" at the chair of zoology and ecology of Belgorod State University. Issue 1. Belgorod: IPC "POLITERRA": 63 pp. [in Russian]
- Sama, G.** 2003. Atlas of the Cerambycidae of Europe and the Mediterranean Area. Volume 1: Northern, Western, Central and Eastern Europe, British Isles and Continental Europe from France (excl. Corsica) to Scandinavia and Urals. Vit Kabourek, Zlín, [2002]: 1-173, 729 figs.
- Sama, G., Rapuzzi, P. & Kairouz, A.** 2010. Catalogue commenté des Cerambycidae du Liban. An annotated catalogue of the Cerambycidae of Lebanon (Insecta Coleoptera Cerambycidae). Quaderni di Studi e Notizie di Storia Naturale della Romagna, 30: 131-201.
- Shapovalov, A. M.** 2012. Longicorn-beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) of Orenburg Region: fauna, distribution, bionomy. Archives of Orenburg Branch of Russian Entomological Society, 3. Orenburg: Orenburg Branch of Russian Entomological Society. 224 pp. [in Russian]
- Villiers, A.** 1967. Contribution à la faune de l'Iran. I. - Coléoptères Cerambycidae. Annales de la Société Entomologique de France (N.S.), 3 (2): 327-379.
- Villiers, A.** 1978. Faune des coléoptères de France I. Cerambycidae. Encyclopédie Entomologique XLII. Paris: Editions Lechevalier, xxvii + 611 pp.
- Volovnik, S. V.** 2024. New faunistic records of beetles (Coleoptera) from Southern Ukraine. Munis Entomology & Zoology, 19 (1): 40-46.
- Winkler, A.** 1929. Catalogus Coleopterorum regionis palaearticae. II. Pars 9-10. Wien: 1009-1264.
- Zamoroka, A. M.** 2022. The longhorn beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) of Ukraine: Results of two centuries of research. Biosystems Diversity, 30 (1): 46-73.